

BETWEEN INVISIBILITY AND PROTAGONISM: POLITICAL PARTICIPATION OF MANINHA XUKURU KARIRI IN THE INDIGENOUS MOVEMENT (1988-2006)¹

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ABSTRACT

This research is the result of an initial analysis of a research project in History that aims to analyze the trajectory of Maninha Xukuru Kariri in the indigenous movement. Through a gender perspective, this research seeks to analyze the protagonism of indigenous women in Alagoas and their political participation. Although we have many women active in the indigenous movement inside and outside their community, they are still largely unknown. Developing studies that seek to bring protagonism to this group is a complex task, as its main obstacle will be the silence about these women in historical productions that often appear as a sex symbol or in the shadows of male personalities. Thus, newspaper clippings from the magazine *Porantim* dated 1989-2006 will be analyzed, analyzing the first female organizations at the national level until arriving at a clipping from Alagoas through the trajectory of Maria Etelvina dos Santos known as Maninha Xukuru Kariri.

Keywords: Women, Indigenous Movement, Alagoas.

INTRODUCTION

During the History degree, under the guidance of professor Michelle Reis de Macedo, research was carried out that resulted in the course completion work on the Protagonism of Indigenous Women in the State of Alagoas (1989-2010) to obtain the undergraduate diploma in History.

This research analyzed the work of Graciliana Wakanã and the founding of the intertribal committee of indigenous women in Alagoas. This organization aimed to encourage and train indigenous women to defend the rights of their community, through the Intertribal

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Committee of Indigenous Women of the Northeast – COIMI, during the period of operation of this committee between 2000 and 2010.

The readings and research carried out to complete the work mentioned above were the beginning of the journey towards the elaboration of this research that will be developed during the course of the Postgraduate program in History at the Federal University of Alagoas, under the guidance of professor Michelle Reis by Macedo.

In this article, I will seek to bring the results of an initial analysis of the research project in History, still ongoing, with the aim of analyzing the political trajectory of Maninha Xukuru Kariri in the indigenous movement. Therefore, this research seeks to analyze the protagonism of this indigenous woman in Alagoas and her political participation.

The interest of History researchers, as in other areas of human sciences, in bringing indigenous women to a prominent place in their community and beyond is growing every day. This reality is due to this group reaching spaces previously unoccupied by men in their community.

In the 2018 elections, two indigenous women gained prominence through their political activities: Sônia Guajajara and Joênia Batista de Carvalho. The first was a candidate for vice-president of the Socialism and Freedom Party (PSOL) and this year was considered one of the 100 most influential people in the world by Times magazine. The second is the first woman elected federal deputy representing Roraima, affiliated with the Sustainability Network (REDE) party.

When we take a look at Alagoas, we have several examples of women who occupied and/or occupy leadership spaces in their community and beyond. Among them, it is important to highlight two names: Nina Katokinn and Maninha Xukuru Kariri. Both women active in the indigenous movement who fought in defense of their people's collective agendas such as territory, health and quality education.

Maria das Graças Soares de Araújo (Nina Katokinn), born on January 31, 1961, was chief and the main leader of the village of the Katokinn people. In the political field, he stood out through participation in meetings with government bodies, demanding the rights of his people, strengthening the defense organization and the fight for health, education and land rights. Unfortunately, due to cancer on March 4, 2022, Nina Katokinn passed away at the age of 71.

We will talk about Maninha Xukuru Kariri later, through newspaper clippings from Revista Porantim. The time frame is from 1988 to 2006, starting with the emergence of the first gender-based indigenous women's organizations and ending with the date of Maninha's death

on October 11, 2006. Her death is remembered as a neglect of indigenous public health neglected by government authorities of Alagoas.

INDIGENOUS PEOPLE: HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Researching indigenous people in the History of Brazil is also knowing the history of the country. Bringing this group as a protagonist is combating stereotypes and prejudices attributed to them to this day that value characteristics of the past, canceling out years of contact with non-indigenous people. In addition, it opposes the valorization of Eurocentric narratives, which nullify indigenous actions or simply reduces them as mere submissive to Portuguese interests. “With laws that oscillated between supporting practices of violence and protecting Indians, the Portuguese and, later, the Brazilians would have managed to defeat, civilize and/or manipulate countless peoples for their own benefit, completely subjugating them, until making them disappear without a trace.” (ALMEIDA, 2017, p.3)

According to Maria Celestino de Almeida, since the 1970s, the history of Brazil has changed, bringing a new approach to numerous topics. Through different sources and a dialogue with other disciplines, it is possible to bring different perspectives on the same subject. The dialogue between History and Anthropology results in readings that transform our past as the most active participation of those who have often been silenced or excluded from the History of Brazil. “The inclusion of new actors and the concern with identifying their actions, choices and interests in the dynamics of their trajectories deconstruct generalizing and simplistic views, opening up a range of new interpretative possibilities on the most varied historical processes” (CARDOSO; VAINFAS, 1997; 2012).

According to the author, among those silenced whose participation in the country's History has been reformulated based on this new approach are indigenous peoples. The analyzes that attribute to these people characteristics such as savages, lazy and that they will disappear begin to value them, bringing a greater contribution to understanding the history of their people and, consequently, knowing even more about the participation of this group in the History of Brazil.

Researching indigenous history is, in a way, studying the formation of the Brazilian people, where they are presented through a duality, between the dominant class and the dominated class. The first is the owner of the capital, land and voice and the second ends up being forgotten, having his story told by someone else. From the moment this reality is rethought, research on indigenous history begins to recognize strategies and confrontations

adopted by them to achieve their objectives.

When thinking about indigenous women, research on the topic becomes even more important, both in social and academic circles, as they are still made invisible because they are indigenous and because they are women. Research that deals with the power of women, whether indigenous or not, ends up reformulating their role in society. Michele Perrot argues that recent feminist research has contributed to the reassessment of women's powers “in its desire to overcome the miserabilist discourse of oppression, to subvert the point of view of domination, it sought to show the presence, the action of women, the plenitude of their roles, and even the coherence of their “culture” and the existence of their powers.” (PERROT, 1928, p.155).

Bringing this point of view to research that deals with indigenous women, it becomes extremely important to know the reality and daily life, understanding in addition to how gender and power relations occur in the indigenous community, we understand how they are conquering spaces hitherto mostly male.

FEMALE SILENCE: ORALITY AS A SOURCE OF RESEARCH

Scholars who research women, whether indigenous or not, in any period of history, face a challenge. When we talk about indigenous women we see this reality clearly; this group, in comparison to the others, does not appear easily in written sources. Because of this, we see little research in History on this topic, something that has been changing, however, at a slow pace. Therefore, it is necessary to briefly reflect on the research sources and methodologies used by those researchers who seek to bring indigenous women as protagonists, not only in the political movement, but in all aspects and at different historical moments.

Researchers who intend to research this group largely carry out research using oral sources and newspaper clippings. For the most part, the newspapers used are those prepared in favor of indigenous causes. Therefore, the historical sources that will be analyzed for the preparation of this research will be found through written sources from newspaper clippings from Revista Porantim and interviews with people who had contact with Maninha Xukuru Kariri, relatives who live in the indigenous region of city of Palmeira dos Índios - Alagoas.

When using oral history as a source of research, it must be understood that some authors agree that the founding of the Oral History Association established oral history as a modern technique of historical documentation, in 1948. With the use of oral sources, a study began, privileging the memories of personalities from the United States. However, only from 1970 onwards, the method was used for interests in issues about indigenous people, black people and

women, for example.

Oral history has given many historians the ability to study topics that are difficult to access in written documents. Through interdisciplinarity, it has contributed significantly to the development of human sciences in several aspects. The appreciation of oral sources, as an object of research, occurred gradually and in conjunction with the evolution of science, starting to value not only the History of great deeds and great personalities, but also culture and different identities of society.

Oral History was and still is highly criticized in relation to its methods and the credibility given to the sources consulted. Many of the criticisms of this new way of making history are due to the use of the method used. Alberti (2008) clarifies that some practices of “militant” oral History, identified in research that intended to achieve the construction of true popular and ideological History as stated by the author, led to mistakes, one of which is the belief that the results obtained from the interview are the story itself, becoming a revelation of reality.

It is up to the historian, when using oral sources, to analyze what is said and what is not said. Silences are also answers. Before going into the field, the historian must have theoretical background on the subject so that the appropriate methodology can be used to carry out the research. Therefore, one should not judge whether something is true or false, both must be analyzed and considered by the researcher.

Amado (1997) argues that the interviewer and the interviewee are interested in the research. Therefore, everything that is said by the interviewee must be narrated by the interviewer and it is up to him to select what meets the proposed study, but always respecting the narrative developed by the first. Therefore, “one cannot expect a single interview or a group of interviews to give a definitive and complete account of what happened in the past” (ALBERTI, 2008, p.158). In the 1970s, the methodology began to be systematized, becoming more academic, becoming more valued in the 1980s and 1990s:

“For a long time, from the positivist perspective predominant in the 19th century, History advocated the written to the detriment of the oral (the latter, identified with the anecdotal, with societies without writing and, therefore, “without History”), and the remote past to the detriment of contemporary themes, in relation to which the historian would not be sufficiently impartial. Later, the emphasis on long-term processes and the preferential study of serial (quantitative) sources, defended by the Annales School (1929), hardly gave space to the role of the individual in History. It was considered that personal accounts, life stories and biographies did not contribute to knowledge of the past, as they are subjective, often distort facts and are unlikely to be representative of a time or a group.” (ALBERTI, 2018, p.16)

PORANTIM: NEWSPAPER CLIPPINGS AS A SOURCE

To use written sources, newspaper clippings from the Porantim magazine, published by CIMI, a body that defends the interests of indigenous people, will be analyzed. When working with newspapers, one must be aware of the bibliography that allows one to understand the challenges in this process, as the newspaper is full of intentions that many historians end up reducing to just the transcription of small excerpts from interviews.

Working with newspaper clippings means going beyond transcribing excerpts from articles to develop analyses. It is necessary to understand all aspects of the newspaper that do not appear to be, but present actions, content and presentation loaded with intentionality. “We therefore deny here those perspectives that take it as a mere “vehicle of information”, an impartial and neutral transmitter of events, an isolated level of the political-social reality in which it is inserted” (LUCA, 2018, p.118) . One of the questions to be answered by historians, who use the newspaper as a research source, according to the author, is to identify the iconographic material, the group responsible for the publication, the group it was intended for, the source of revenue, among others.

When using the Porantim newspaper as a research source, these aspects must be taken into consideration, as it says a lot about how the newspaper is presented and which articles are chosen. As it is a newspaper with an initiative to support the indigenous movement and financed by institutions that defend these causes, we will find articles, photographs, cartoons that are loaded with intentions, which in this case is the defense and dissemination of indigenous interests and violence that these peoples they face, often caused by the lack of interest from the state and the actions of farmers in the region.

Furthermore, it is worth highlighting and analyzing during the research where and how indigenous women appear in these newspapers. Therefore, not only the article mentioning this particular group should be considered, but the entire newspaper. What space is given to indigenous women in the Porantim newspaper? In my consultation, the spaces designated for this group reinforced the position of the home and rarely became covers.

The newspaper is far from being an impartial source, as previously stated, its entire creation is full of intentionality that must be considered. "It can be admitted, in light of the epistemological trajectory of the discipline and without implying the interposition of any limit or obstacle to the use of newspapers and magazines, that the periodical press selects, orders, structures and narrates, in a certain way, what is elected as worthy of reaching the public” (LUCA,2018, p.139). Therefore, according to the same author, the historian must have tools

that problematize the event, which according to her, is not exclusive only to the press text.

“The considerations point, therefore, to a type of use of the periodical press that is not limited to extracting one or another text from isolated authors, however representative they may be, but rather prescribes a detailed analysis of their place of insertion and outlines an approach which makes printed materials, at the same time, a source and object of historiographical research, rigorously inserted into competent criticism” (LUCA, 2018, p.141).

In addition to these, newspaper clippings from Porantim magazine from 1988 to 2016 will also be used. This documentary collection is available on the Armazém Memória website, which is characterized as a virtual reference center on indigenous issues in different historical contexts. The newspaper Porantim has been published by the Indigenous Missionary Council - CIMI since 1979, according to it, Porantim means: oar, weapon and memory.

It is worth mentioning that CIMI was created in a historical period when the country was governed by the military and the aim was to achieve the country's development. In pursuit of this objective, the government neglected its actions by taking away the rights of the people, including indigenous peoples. With the construction of the Transamazônica Highway (BR-230), which for many represented economic development, for others, the indigenous peoples, it represented the destruction of their territory. It was then, during this period, that CIMI was born with the main objective of providing support to indigenous people in different activities, training their missionaries, to defend indigenous interests, one of these actions being the edition of the Porantim newspaper that we will work on in this research.

It is worth remembering the importance of the Armazém Memória website in the construction of research on different people and at different historical moments. The site is an initiative for the articulation and collective construction of a website that aims to develop public policies that can guarantee researchers and citizens access to different historical memories.

Armazém Memória brings together digitally: collections of periodicals, testimonials, books, videos, audios, articles, documents and images; works of a historical, legal and educational nature. Through Video libraries, Image Collections, Virtual Reference Centers and Thematic Collections in smart libraries.

“Armazém Memória is a movement that is structured as a network, where the website is the sum of the efforts of a collective action of people and institutions interested in building a public policy of access to national memory. The construction of this digital collection aims to integrate the countless efforts to guard, access and rescue the memory of the popular struggle that are carried out in our country, being at the same time a challenge of establishing full citizenship, seeking to exchange experiences between generations a country for all Brazilians.” (ZELIC, 2017)

SISTER XUKURU KARIRI: POLITICAL TRAJECTORY

Developing studies that seek to bring indigenous women to the forefront is complex work, as the main obstacle will be the silence about these women in historical productions, who often appear as sexual symbols or in the shadows of male personalities. “Their experiences need to be told against the silence, violations and discrimination imposed by the colonization of indigenous peoples” (SAMPAIO, 2015, p.9).

Only in this way can we highlight those who are normally forgotten due to their double invisibility because they are women and because they are indigenous. Despite this current visibility, the participation of indigenous women in the political field is not something recent, their markedly gender-based organizations began to emerge with more intensity in the middle of the second half of the 1990s, as stated by Sacchi (2003).

Regardless of whether indigenous women's organizations have emerged recently, it does not mean that they did not participate in political decisions in the interest of their community. Ortolan Matos (2012) argues that indigenous women were not alienated from decision-making and to explain his position he argues “it is necessary to reposition the analytical perspective to be able to see the difference in profiles between the public sphere and the private sphere when experienced in indigenous societies and in same spheres when experienced in non-indigenous societies” (MATOS, 2012, p.147).

To defend her position, the author clarifies that spaces considered private among non-indigenous people can have other meanings. Ethnographic studies, as the author argues, record more intense female political participation in discussions held in family environments, a space not considered public among non-indigenous people. Despite not being on the front line, that was where they were positioned.

From 1990 onwards, the first indigenous women's organizations emerged, in a complementary way to the struggle of male leaders, as stated by Matos (2012). The first instance to deal with women's issues was created in May 2001, according to VERDUM (2008), composed of a department that is part of COIAB with the aim of defending women's rights and their specific demands. From then on, women began to organize themselves in meetings, the first of which was held nationwide in 2006 by the Department of Indigenous Women of COIAB with the support of the Institute of Socioeconomic Studies (INESC).

Indigenous female organizations, when holding meetings and workshops to plan their actions, did not only consider gender particularities. By gaining a voice inside and outside their community, they sought to plan their actions in line with the general indigenous movement, or

rather, their agendas did not exclude demands that would ensure the survival and reaffirmation of their identity.

We can better understand this articulation in the newspaper clipping from Revista Porantim, Cimi's printed newspaper, dated November 1998. It talks about the first meeting of leaders from BA, ES and MG, in this event, in addition to women, discussing participation in the indigenous movement also sought to discuss the problems affecting their community. Among them, the lack of land, hunger, lack of water, medical assistance, discrimination, lack of schools, security, transportation and lack of freedom were highlighted. This event was also attended by Maninha Xukuru Kariri, who we will talk about later, who was advising the event with other indigenous people from different regions.

The history of indigenous people in Brazil and in particular Alagoas involves slavery, exploitation and expulsion from their lands. A story that has in common with those of other indigenous peoples: the struggle to regain their territory, access to education, quality healthcare and the preservation of their culture. When researching indigenous issues, one must also analyze these agendas and when researching these women's organizations and Maninha Xukuru Kariri, one must talk about their role in the indigenous movement in defending these essential rights for the survival and maintenance of their community, as their agendas did not exclude these claims.

The trajectory of Maninha Xukuru Kariri is directly linked to the history of her people, called Xukuru-Kariri, which has this name due to the coexistence of two ethnicities: Xukuru and Kariri, both present to this day in northeastern Brazil. The majority live on traditional land and in the urban area of the municipality of Palmeiras dos Índios, in Alagoas. Although Maninha has great importance in the indigenous struggle not only in Alagoas, but also in the defense of the lands of different indigenous peoples in Brazil, her invisibility also falls and, to date, it has not been possible to find any study that deals with her actions. in the indigenous movement.

Maninha Xukuru Kariri, was born in 1966 and dreamed of studying medicine. When he went to Recife to take a pre-university exam, in less than a year he ended up returning to his community, giving up on his dream, as Funai paid for a few months of the pre-university course. He returned to his city where he then began to advise his father Antônio Celestino, writing down commitments and considerations about meetings and events that were held with the community. It was from then on that he began to become interested in the demands of his people, reaching spaces that go beyond his region.

In 1990, the East-Northeast commission was created, consisting of eight indigenous

leaders, Maninha was the only woman in the group. In 1995, at the APOINME creation meeting, Maninha was the only woman in coordination and in many meetings she was the only woman among the leaders. The October 1994 newspaper clipping from Porantim magazine, with the title “The example of women”, praises Maninha's courage in not being intimidated, despite death threats and invitations to spend the night with farmers. In this same excerpt, Maninha denounces the reality of the indigenous people of Fazenda Canto at that time, where they ended up subjecting themselves to slave labor in neighboring sugarcane fields, receiving 1 real per ton of cut sugarcane. Maninha Xukuru is highlighted by other women as a symbol of resistance, demanding respect and compliance with the constitution that guarantees land and autonomy.

According to the website Mulher 500 anos, she was the first woman to be part of the Articulation of Indigenous Peoples of the Northeast, Minas Gerais and Espírito Santos (Apoime). Maninha contributed and encouraged other women to conquer spaces in environments that were mostly male, having autonomy and awareness of themselves, defending their interests as indigenous people and also their particularities as a woman.

Rosane Lacerda, former Cimi Legal Advisor, in November 2006, published a text in Porantim magazine entitled “Goodbye, great warrior Xucuru Kariri”. In this newspaper clipping, Rosane reveals that Maninha did not talk about the topic of gender, but acted. “In meetings, as in APOINME tasks or in caravans across the country, he was always the personification of responsibility, prudence, consideration, balance. He spoke gently, but with authority. She was respected. He had, as he liked to say, the blood of the Celestinos and the Santanas.” according to the author.

Maninha Xukuru Kariri passed away on October 11, 2006, after having breathing problems and suffering a cardiac arrest. His death was a great loss for the indigenous movement and felt by different people in different states of Brazil. Following this, many demonstrations were held with the aim of publicizing and defending the rights of indigenous peoples such as access to quality healthcare. The death of Maninha Xukuru Kariri is a symbol of the state's neglect and the poor quality of medical care, in particular, for the indigenous peoples of the Palmeira dos Índios - AL region.

Based on the above, the time frame was delimited considering the beginning of the emergence of indigenous women's organizations in Brazil. From 1980 onwards, we can find only two indigenous women's organizations: the association of Indigenous Women of Alto Rio Negro (AMARN) and Association of Indigenous Women of Taracua, Rio Uapés and Tiquié (AMITRUT), according to Sacchi (2003). However, it was from 1990 onwards that these

organizations emerged more intensely. The time frame begins with the beginning of Maninha's participation in political environments, which coincides with the emergence of the first markedly gender-based organizations and ends with the date of her death in 2006, which resulted in several demonstrations across the country.

CONCLUSION

Researching indigenous women means understanding that they were often silenced during various periods in Brazil's history. Although at present, some of them have achieved a prominent place within the indigenous movement and outside it, there are still few. Still, it is important to highlight that these groups are reaching spaces that were previously difficult for men to occupy, whether they are indigenous or not.

Maninha Xukuru Kariri held leadership positions at a time when it was unusual to find women in this space. During visits to communities, she always sought to encourage other women to organize themselves and occupy spaces beyond the domestic environment, defending the recovery of land, health and quality education. Gender issues were not always in the discussions, but the presence of a woman in places where she was often the only one, in organizations where she was the only member, says a lot about her importance as an influence for other indigenous women.

Regarding this, Ortolan Matos uses the term ethnic essentialism, according to the author, indigenous women are in a duality where they defend the interests of the general indigenous movement and other specific gender issues. Paula Faustino, on the other hand, refers to indigenous women as indigenous women, the exchanges of words represent that this group places the defense of indigenous interests as essential.

Many questions can be asked, research that puts this group in the spotlight can help to counter the images that still persist about this group, contrary to the imaginary that places them as sinful, sexualized and necessary only as procreators.

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